

Cerium(III) catalysis in acid bromate oxidation of citric acid in the presence of bromo-complex-forming metal ions

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Abstract : Cerium(III) ion-catalysed bromate oxidation of citric acid in aqueous acetic acid media containing HClO_4 and mercury(II), a bromo-complex-forming metal ion, exhibits first-order in [bromate] and less than unit order in [citric acid] and [cerium(III)]. Reaction rate increases linearly with an increase in $[\text{HClO}_4]$. However, an opposite effect is observed with $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ and $[\text{NaHSO}_4]$. D_2O and $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$ have insignificant effect on the rate of reaction. The catalytic effect of Ce^{III} ion is displayed by its complex forming ability and in the proposed mechanism it is assumed that acid bromate reacts with the Ce^{III} -citric acid binary complex, whose formation (K_c) is precedent to the bromate-cerium(III) reaction, and results a ternary complex (K_f), which subsequently decomposes (kd) into products with the regeneration of Ce^{III} . The effects of ionic strength and dielectric constant of the media are also in accordance with the proposed mechanism. The reaction constants (K_c , K_f and kd) involved in the envisaged mechanism are evaluated. There is a good agreement between the observed and the calculated rate constants under different experimental conditions.

Keywords : Cerium(III) catalysis, citric acid, bromate oxidation.

The use of cerium(III), a lanthanoid metal ion, as a catalyst in the oxidation of organic compounds by Br^{V} alone, unmixed by competing/faster oxidation by the generated molecular bromine from bromate-bromide autocatalytic reaction, is of particular interest. No instance of cerium(III) ion catalysis of any oxidation was reported until it was briefly reported in bromate-oxalic acid/malic acid reactions^{1,2}. However, cerium(III) is being used in many Belousov-Zhabotinskii (B-Z) oscillating reactions³⁻¹². Oscillating reactions generally involve one or two autocatalytic reactions that turn each other on and off in a manner somewhat analogous to the *flip-flop* circuit in electronics. An important characteristics of the chemical mechanism suggested for the B-Z reaction is that a key role is attributed to Br^- ion, an intermediate of the reaction^{3,4}. If Br^- ions are trapped, by adding a suitable complexing agent, the autocatalytic reaction(s) stops and the chemical oscillation is completely quenched¹². This is exactly what is observed with the addition of mercury(II) or thallium(III) ions to the oscillating systems^{1,2}. Added ions form stable mercury(II)/thallium(III)-bromo-complexes of high stability constants¹³. Hence, all the bromide ions are fixed and cannot react further. At higher concentrations of these $\text{Hg}^{\text{II}}/\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}$ ions, the reaction mechanism is expected to be different from the B-Z reaction. Therefore in the

present study, in order to know the operating mechanism of the hitherto unreported, the substrate citric acid, a biologically important hydroxy acid, has been used. The mechanism underlying the reaction is discussed and all the reaction constants involved in the mechanism proposed are evaluated.

Results and discussion

The experimental conditions employed are opposite to those necessary for the oscillatory systems. The kinetic complexity, either observed or anticipated, is eliminated by employing bromo-complex-forming metal $\{\text{Hg}^{\text{II}}/\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}\}$ ions. Preliminary experiments showed that mercury(II) is more suitable as a complexing agent because it has to play only two roles. One is by complexing Br^- ions as HgBr^+ ($K_1 = 2.51 \times 10^8 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) and HgBr_2 ($K_2 = 3.8 \times 10^8 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$; Ref. 13), which eliminate the autocatalytic production of bromine ($\text{BrO}_3^- + 5\text{Br}^- + 6\text{H}^+ \rightleftharpoons 3\text{Br}_2 + 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and the subsequent citric acid-bromine reaction. The other is by inhibiting oscillations. Initially added mercuric acetate over a wide concentration range (0.001 to 0.01 mol dm^{-3}) did not produce any effect other than complexing bromide ions.

Under pseudo-first-order conditions, the disappearance rate of [bromate] followed first-order rate law as is seen

from good linear plots ($r \geq 0.998$; $s \leq 0.035$) of \log [bromate] versus time for more than two half-lives. Further k_1 (s^{-1}) is independent of initial bromate concentration (Table 1). Under the experimental conditions, the uncatalysed bromate-citric acid redox reaction rate is negligible ($k_1 \approx 10^{-7}$, s^{-1}) compared to the catalysed reaction rate. Hence, the obtained rate constants and thermodynamic parameters pertain to catalysed reaction only.

The rate of oxidation increases with an increase in substrate concentration (Table 1) and the plot of $\log k_1$ versus \log [citric acid] is linear ($r = 0.999$, $s = 0.027$) with a slope value of 0.75 ± 0.05 . Further, the rates are following the Michaelis-Menten's type of correlation (Fig. 1a). By adding small amounts of cerium(III) sulphate, the very slow Br^V -citric acid redox reaction is found to

be accelerated (Table 1) and the plot of $\log k_1$ versus \log [cerium(III)] is linear ($r = 0.997$, $s = 0.030$) with a slope value of 0.80 ± 0.05 . A change in $[NaClO_4]$ had no effect on the rate of reaction (Table 2). The value of k_1 increases linearly with an increase in $[HClO_4]$ (Table 1) and a slope of 0.96 ± 0.01 ($r = 0.999$, $s = 0.024$) is obtained when $\log k_1$ is plotted against $\log [HClO_4]$. However, a decrease in rate with an increase in $[H_2SO_4]/[NaHSO_4]$ is observed (Table 2). The rate constant increases with an increase in the percentage of acetic acid in the solvent composition (Table 2), and the plot of $\log k_1$ versus $1/D$ ($D =$ dielectric constant of the medium) is linear with a positive slope ($r = 0.997$, $s = 0.037$). The inertness of the solvent acetic acid towards oxidant has been tested earlier. The reaction rate is unaffected by carrying out the reaction in D_2O .

Table 1. Effect of varying [bromate], [substrate], [acid] and $[Ce^{III}]$ on the rate of reaction at 303 ± 0.1 K

$10^3 [Br^V]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^2 [Citric\ acid]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^4 [Ce^{III}]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$[HClO_4]^c$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^4 k_1$ (s ⁻¹)	
				Exptl. ^a	Calcd. ^b
0.4	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.67	1.66
0.8	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.66	1.67
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.66	1.65
1.2	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.68	1.68
1.6	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.66	1.69
2.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.67	1.68
1.0	0.5	1.0	1.0	0.91	0.92
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.66	1.68
1.0	1.5	1.0	1.0	2.22	2.25
1.0	3.0	1.0	1.0	3.70	3.71
1.0	4.0	1.0	1.0	4.16	4.13
1.0	6.0	1.0	1.0	5.26	5.25
1.0	10.0	1.0	1.0	6.25	6.30
1.0	1.0	0.5	1.0	1.00	1.03
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.66	1.68
1.0	1.0	2.0	1.0	2.82	2.80
1.0	1.0	4.0	1.0	4.47	4.50
1.0	1.0	6.0	1.0	6.33	6.38
1.0	1.0	8.0	1.0	7.85	7.81
1.0	1.0	10.0	1.0	8.92	8.95
1.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.88 (1.90)*	0.90 (1.91)*
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.67 (1.78)	1.66 (1.70)
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.5	2.29 (1.74)	2.20 (1.72)
1.0	1.0	1.0	2.0	3.14 (1.67)	3.06 (1.66)
1.0	1.0	1.0	2.5	4.01 (1.57)	4.11 (1.58)

$[Hg(OAc)_2] = 0.005$ mol dm⁻³; $HOAc-H_2O = 30-70\%$ (v/v).

^aMean of duplicate experiments. ^bCalculated using eqn. (2).

^cAcid effect is carried out at constant ionic strength ($NaClO_4/NaHSO_4$).

*Parentheses values are obtained in H_2SO_4 medium.

Fig. 1. Dependence of rate on substrate and catalyst concentrations at 303 ± 0.1 K. Other conditions as in Tables 1 and 2. (a) Representative Michaelis-Menten's plot. (b) Plot of $1/k_1$ versus $1/[\text{cerium(III)}]$.

The possible formation of free radicals as intermediates is investigated by adding radical scavengers to the reaction mixture. When acrylonitrile/acrylamide monomer (0.01 mol dm^{-3}) is added to the reaction in a typical kinetic experiment, the reaction rate decreased by $\sim 15\%$, and when, 2,4,6-tri-tert-butylphenol ($1.6 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, a stronger radical scavenger) is added to the reaction mixture, the reaction rate decreased by $\sim 40\%$. Moreover, when 0.7 mol dm^{-3} of acrylonitrile/acrylamide monomer is added to the reaction mixture polymeric species are observed after a few minutes in a nitrogen atmosphere. These facts indicate the generation of free radicals in the reaction. Further, there is no polymer formation when acrylic monomers are added separately to reaction mixtures of bromate-citric acid (uncatalysed reaction), cerium(III)-bromate and cerium(III)-citric acid in the presence of mercuric acetate.

Activation parameters viz. E_a , ΔH^\ddagger , ΔS^\ddagger and ΔG^\ddagger obtained by the linear least-square fittings of $\log k_1$ versus $1/T$ plots are: 79.77 ($*82.05$) $\pm 1.3 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, 77.25 ($*79.53$) $\pm 1.3 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, -68.54 ($-*72.47$) $\pm 2.5 \text{ J deg}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ and 98.02 ($*101.49$) $\pm 1.4 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ in HClO_4

Table 2. Dependence of rate on solvent composition, $[\text{NaHSO}_4]$ and $[\text{NaClO}_4]$ at 303 ± 0.1 K

HOAc-H ₂ O % (v/v)	$10^4 k_1$ (s ⁻¹)	$[\text{NaHSO}_4]^s$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^4 k_1$ (s ⁻¹)	$[\text{NaClO}_4]^p$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^4 k_1$ (s ⁻¹)
10-90 (66.6)*	0.76	0.10	1.99	0.10	1.80
20-80 (59.9)	1.15	0.25	1.71	0.25	1.77
30-70 (53.2)	1.80	0.50	1.17	0.50	1.79
40-60 (46.5)	3.12	0.75	1.00	1.00	1.81
50-50 (39.8)	5.13	1.00	0.88	—	—

$[\text{KBrO}_3] = 0.001 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{citric acid}] = 0.01 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{acid}] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{Ce}^{\text{III}}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

(s) At molar sulphuric acid. (p) At molar perchloric acid.

*Values in parentheses are the dielectric constant of the medium.

medium ($*\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$ medium) respectively at 303 K.

The cerous ion catalysis in acid bromate oxidation of citric acid could be explained in two alternative ways and one of them is the oxidation of organic substrate by ceric ion resulting from bromate-cerium(III) autocatalytic reaction. If the mechanism suggested by Noyes *et al.*^{3,4,14} is applied to the oxidation of cerium(III) with no Br^- ion involved, the set of elementary reactions (R1) and (R2) are obtained. Where BrO_2^\bullet is a radical species which in turn is responsible for the oxidation of cerium(III). An autocatalytic reaction (R3) for bromous acid is obtained from reactions (R1) and (R2).

Thus, the initial rate of cerium(IV) formation is considered to be twice that of bromate consumption.

In the bromate-cerium(III) reaction, Yoshida *et al.*¹⁵ observed an induction period (IP) (20 min under the conditions of the present study, without Hg^{II} ions) and duration of the IP increased with decrease in $[\text{bromate}]_0$ and $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]_0$, and was independent of $[\text{cerium(III)}]_0$. The reaction also exhibited second order in $[\text{bromate}]_0$. On the other hand, in the presence of mercury(II), the present reaction exhibits first-order in $[\text{bromate}]_0$ and no induction period is observed over a wide range of $[\text{bromate}]_0$, $[\text{substrate}]_0$ and $[\text{cerium(III)}]_0$.

Bromate cannot oxidise Ce^{III} and Mn^{II} ions significantly in perchloric acid medium^{3,4}. This conclusion is also consistent with the complete failure to obtain oscillations in perchloric acid medium^{3,4}. However, in the present study the oxidation rates obtained in HClO_4 and H_2SO_4 media are comparable. The obtained data therefore, discard

the route through the FKN mechanism^{3,4}. The other possibility is the attribution of a direct oxidation of Ce^{III}-citric acid complex to Ce^{IV}-citric acid complex which subsequently decomposes into products.

The marked increase in rate with the addition of Ce^{III} ions indicates that, citric acid forms a complex with Ce^{III} ion in which the redox potential (E^0) for the Ce^{III}S/Ce^{IV}S couple ($S = \text{substrate}$) will be less than that of the Ce^{III}_{aq}/Ce^{IV}_{aq} couple (1.44 V vs NHE). Determination of E^0 value for the Ce^{III}/Ce^{IV}-citric acid couple was unsuccessful because of the instability in the system. However, E^0 value was evaluated (as 0.58 vs NHE) in Mn^{II}-catalysed bromate oxidation of citric acid¹⁶. If such complexing was not involved, a similar Ce^{III} ion catalytic efficiency should have been observed with other organic substrates like alcohols, diols, carboxylic acids, carbonyl compounds oxidation by bromate, however it is not.

Figs. 1a and 1b also illustrate the oxidation of citric acid has a dependence on [substrate] and [catalyst], is consistent with the Michaelis-Menten's kinetics; the reversible formation of Ce^{III} complex with one mole of the substrate must precede the rate-determining oxidation step.

In aqueous solutions, Ce^{III} forms a 1 : 1 complex with citric acid. Even though efforts have failed to isolate this

complex, the stability constant ($\log \beta$) of the complex is calculated as 3.88 ± 0.5 at 30 °C and 1.0 mol dm⁻³ ionic strength, which is in accordance with the earlier reports¹⁷

In acid solutions, the reactive species of bromate are likely to be BrO₃⁻ and protonated bromate¹⁸ {HOBrO₂ or OBr⁺(OH)₂/(Br⁺O₂)}. The acceleration in rate of reaction with an increase in [HClO₄], and the results of dielectric constant and ionic strength effects on the rate of reaction indicate HOBrO₂ is the active species of the oxidant taking part in the oxidation. In acid solution (pH < 5) hydrolysis of Ce^{III} ion can be neglected and the hexaaquo ion likely represents the major species of cerium(III).

Addition of D₂O brought about no change in the reaction rate, which rules out the possibility of protonation of citric acid prior to the rate-determining oxidation step. Citric acid dissociates slightly ($pK_{a1} = 3.08$, $pK_{a2} = 4.74$ and $pK_{a3} = 6.40$ at 18 °C) and it is probable that cerous ion in HClO₄/H₂SO₄ media forms a complex prevailing with the undissociated and unprotonated substrate molecule.

Based on the aforesaid reasons and in light of the experimental results, the oxidative mechanism as shown in Scheme 1 is proposed.

Scheme 1

The rate-determining oxidation step involves transfer of an electron from the formed 1 : 1 Ce^{III}-citric acid complex to Br^V in the coordinated stage (complex), as a result of which Ce^{IV}-citrate complex is formed. The Ce^{IV}-citrate complex decomposes into products in a fast step with the regeneration of Ce^{III}. Spectrophotometric determination of the Ce^{IV}-citrate complex was unsuccessful because of its short life. However, evidence for the formation of Ce^{IV}-citrate complex was obtained from the UV-Visible spectra with bathochromic shift of about 8 nm from 317.5 nm to 326 nm together with hyperchromicity at 326 nm (λ_{max} of Ce^{IV} is 317.5 nm with $\epsilon = 5440 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$).

Substrates forming five-membered rings are oxidised much more rapidly than if the rings are six-membered⁴. The catalytic efficiency of Ce^{III} ion in the present system may be due to formation of five-membered ring complexes.

HBrO₂ is a two equivalent oxidant, strong enough to consume many more organic substrates. HBrO₂, thus formed (Scheme 1) oxidises substrate/intermediate in fast steps and finally converts to bromide ion.

The quantitative estimation of the bromoacetone precipitate^{19a} indicates that more than 80% of acetonedicarboxylic acid is produced per mole of citric acid under kinetic conditions (with 1 : 10 [oxidant] : [substrate] ratio). This is similar to the observation made by Mehrotra in V^V oxidation²⁰ and Sengupta in Ce^{IV} oxidation²¹. However, with excess of [bromate], formic acid is the final product of oxidation^{19b}. This might be formed through acetone, which is formed by the successive decarboxylations of two carboxyl groups of the acetonedicarboxylic acid as in the case of citric acid oxidation by permanganate²². The formed acetone undergoes oxidation to give formic acid through enolisation²³.

The proposed mechanism leads to the following rate expression.

$$\frac{-d[\text{BrO}_3^-]/dt}{[\text{BrO}_3^-]_{\text{T}}} = k_1 = \frac{kdK_pK_cK_f [\text{citric acid}] [\text{Ce}^{\text{III}}] [\text{H}^+]}{1 + K_p [\text{H}^+] + K_pK_cK_f [\text{citric acid}] [\text{Ce}^{\text{III}}][\text{H}^+]} \quad (1)$$

where, K_p is the protonation constant of BrO₃⁻ and is as 0.51 dm³ mol⁻¹ at 30 °C (Ref. 18) and kd denotes the decomposition constant of the ternary complex. At 1.0 mol dm⁻³ acid, after substituting K_p value and taking reciprocal, the eq. (1) reduces to the eq. (2).

$$\frac{1}{k_1} = \frac{2.96}{kd K_c K_f [\text{citric acid}] [\text{Ce}^{\text{III}}]} + \frac{1}{kd} \quad (2)$$

According to eq. (2) the plots of $1/k_1$ versus $1/[\text{citric acid}]$ and $1/k_1$ against $1/[\text{cerium(III)}]$ should be linear with a definite (same) intercept on y-axis. Such a realisation (Figs. 1a and 1b; $r = 0.998$, $s = 0.030$; $r = 0.997$, $s = 0.038$, respectively), supports the proposed mechanism (Scheme 1). From the intercept and slope data of Fig. 1a or Fig. 1b, the decomposition constant (kd) and the formation constant (K_f) of the citric acid-Ce^{III}-Br^V ternary complex can be calculated with the knowledge of the obtained formation constant of Ce^{III}-citric acid complex ($K_c = 7.6 \times 10^3$, with 5% error). These are: $kd = 1.05 \pm 0.07 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $K_f = 84.37 \pm 0.1 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ at 30 °C. Using these obtained values, the rate constants under different experimental conditions were calculated by eq. (2) and compared with the experimental data. There is a good agreement between them (Table 1), which also supports the envisaged mechanism.

The mechanism is further corroborated by the solvent influence on the reaction rate. The ternary complex, substrate-Ce^{III}-Br^V, is less polar than are the reactants due to dispersal of charge, hence, decreasing polarity of the solvent media is expected to stabilise the citric acid-Ce^{III}-bromate ternary complex in preference to the reactants thereby enhancing the reaction rate. Such a solvent influence has actually been observed (Table 2). The inhibitory effect of H₂SO₄ and HSO₄⁻ may be due to formation of the CeSHSO₄ complex, in which concentration of the active Ce^{III}-S complex decreases thereby a decrease in the reaction rate with increasing concentration of H₂SO₄/HSO₄⁻.

The negative entropy of activation suggests that the activated complex is more stabilised than are the reactants. The value of ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger were both favourable for the electron transfer process. The value of ΔS^\ddagger within the range of radical reactions, has been ascribed to the nature of electron pairing and electron unpairing processes and to the loss of a degree of freedom, formerly available to the reactions on the formation of a rigid transition state.

In conclusion, in the presence of mercury(II), a bromo-complexing metal ion, citric acid-Ce^{III}-bromate reaction does not route through the FKN mechanism. Complex formation between cerium(III) and citric acid takes precedence over the bromate-cerium(III) reaction, and acid bromate reacts with the formed Ce^{III}-citric acid binary complex resulting in a ternary complex, which subsequently decomposes into identifiable products.

Experimental

Materials : Citric acid (A.R., Fluka) was recrystallised twice from 1 : 1 acetone-benzene and used. $\text{Ce}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (A.R., Merck) was dissolved in aqueous mineral acid solution and used after standardisation. D_2O (purity 99.4%) was obtained from BARC, Mumbai, India. KBrO_3 (Reidel), $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$ (Merck) were of highest purity. All other chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade and their solutions were prepared either in redistilled water or in purified acetic acid.

Kinetic measurements : A large excess (10 to 100-fold) of [substrate] was used for all kinetic measurements. The reactions were allowed to run in a nitrogen atmosphere and in dark, their kinetics were followed by estimating [bromate] iodometrically at regular time intervals. The first-order plots were linear ($r \geq 0.998$, $s \leq 0.03$) to 80% completion. Pseudo-first-order rate constants (k_1 , s^{-1}) were calculated from the slopes of the plots of \log [bromate] versus time. The reaction rates were not affected by stirring. The rate constants obtained from multiple determinations were within $\pm 5\%$ of each other. A Shimadzu multipurpose recording double beam spectrophotometer model MPS 5000 equipped with a temperature controller was used for absorption studies.

Product analysis : Acetonedicarboxylic acid/formic acid product was analysed by literature method¹⁹. Carbon dioxide formed as the product of oxidation was analysed by bubbling a nitrogen gas through the reaction mixture and passing the liberated gas through a U-shaped tube containing a saturated $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ solution. Bromide ion was estimated by adding a silver nitrate solution, resulting in the formation of a pale yellow precipitate (AgBr).

Formation constant of the cerium(III)-citric acid complex was determined at 30 °C using different least-square methods. Irving-Rossotti expression²⁴ was used for the calculation of \bar{n}_A , \bar{n} and pL .

Regression analysis of the experimental data to obtain the regression coefficient (r) and standard deviation (s), of points from regression line was performed using a Pentium-IV personal computer.

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